

(fig., a). This indicates a short incubation period of 1 h can be recommended.

ARA of whole and cut plants incubated in darkness did not differ significantly. However, ARA of whole plants incubated in darkness was significantly lower (about 40%) than that of whole plants in light. It is more convenient to use cut plants in measuring ARA because they require smaller incubation vessels (plastic bags) and less acetylene-air

mixture than whole plants. Dark incubation also eliminates the need for extra light facilities.

ARA was highest between 1300 and 1600 h (fig. b), and at acetylene concentration of 10-15% (fig., c). A 4-h interval between sampling and assay significantly reduced ARA compared with a 1-h interval (fig., d). It seems important to process the plants (field sampling, washing, cutting, and sealing in plastic

bags, etc.) as quickly as possible. Four persons can sample and assay about 40 plants/h.

If an experiment involves ARA measurements on a large number of plants, it may be advisable to assay only half the desired number one day and half the following day: no significant difference in ARA was obtained from samples taken two consecutive days (fig., e). ■

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effect of leaf cutting for rice herbage on grain yield of deepwater rice

T. Kupkanchanakul, K. Kupkanchanakul, and S. Rontun, Huntra Rice Experiment Station, Ayutthaya 13000, Thailand

Rice herbage could be very important in deepwater areas where natural pasture for grazing is minimal. We studied the effect of time and frequency of leaf cutting for herbage on grain yield of deepwater rice in 1987 wet season.

Dry seeds of Thai variety Pin Gaew 56 were broadcast at 120 kg/ha on plowed soil 25 May. Seedlings emerged 4 Jun.

Five treatments were arranged in randomized complete block design with four replications (see table). Rice leaves were cut at the collar of the last fully developed leaf, at different times.

Effect of leaf removal on herbage yield, grain yield, and yield components of Pin Gaew 56.^a Huntra Rice Experiment Station, Ayutthaya, Thailand, 1987 wet season.

Cutting time	Herbage (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Yield components				
			Panicles (no./m ²)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Fertility (%)	1000-grain wt (g)	Plant height (cm)
No cutting	—	2.02 bc	127	91	79	26.6	237 a
40 DAE	0.7 c	2.13 abc	134	85	84	26.8	221 b
70 DAE	0.7 c	2.20 ab	135	85	77	26.5	223 b
100 DAE	1.0 b	2.24 a	143	92	82	27.1	223 b
40 + 100 DAE	1.4 a	1.94 c	126	83	81	26.5	217 b
CV (%)	11.0	6.30	25.5	15.0	6.9	8.4	6.9

^aIn a column, values followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Grain yield was significantly improved by leaf cutting 100 d after emergence (DE), and was not affected by leaf cutting at 40 and 70 DE nor by double cutting at 40 and 100 DE.

Herbage yield was highest with double cutting at 40 and 100 DE. Herbage

production in one cutting and grain yield were highest with cutting at 100 DE. Plant height was significantly reduced by leaf cutting. This might have contributed to increased panicle number, which improved yield. ■

Fertilizer management

Nitrogen substitution with *Sesbania rostrata* in rice production

A. S. Halepyati and M. N. Sheelavantar, Agronomy Division, University of Agricultural Sciences, Dharwar 580005, Karnataka, India

We studied the effect of *S. rostrata* incorporation on N economy of irrigated transplanted rice. Field experiments were conducted during 1987 and 1988 wet season in a factorial randomized block design with four replications. Soil was black clay loam with pH 7.8, 541.0 kg total N, 12.9 kg available P/ha, and 323.6

kg K/ha. Rice received varying N, 22 kg P, 41.5 kg K/ha.

S. rostrata was sown the last week of Jun and incorporated at 55 d old, 1 d before rice was transplanted. Total

biomass and N accumulation were determined at incorporation.

S. rostrata with higher plant density had the highest biomass production and N accumulation at incorporation (Table 1).

Table 1. Biomass and N accumulation in *S. rostrata*.

Sesbania population density	Biomass (t/ha)			N accumulation (kg/ha)		
	1987	1988	Pooled mean	1987	1988	Pooled mean
Low (333,000 plants/ha)	15.33	16.36	15.84	129.72	139.41	134.57
Medium (444,000 plants/ha)	18.07	19.07	18.57	151.49	160.73	156.11
High (666,000 plants/ha)	22.43	23.61	23.02	172.03	183.37	177.70
Mean	18.61	19.68	19.14	151.08	161.17	156.13
LSD (0.05)	0.41	0.51	0.34	15.24	11.74	11.17

Table 2. Effect of *S. rostrata* (SR) on rice grain yield, straw yield, and nutrient uptake of rice.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)			Straw yield (t/ha)			N uptake (kg/ha)		
	1987	1988	Pooled mean	1987	1988	Pooled mean	1987	1988	Pooled mean
SR only	3.6	5.5	4.6	5.8	7.5	6.7	35.60	55.86	45.78
SR + 25 kg N/ha	3.9	5.9	4.9	6.1	8.0	7.0	35.34	58.79	47.06
SR + 50 kg N/ha	4.2	6.3	5.3	6.1	8.3	7.2	39.57	63.17	51.37
SR + 75 kg N/ha	4.5	6.7	5.6	6.4	8.4	7.4	43.49	67.49	55.49
SR+ 100 kg N/ha	4.9	6.9	5.9	6.0	8.8	7.4	43.62	71.94	57.78
Control (100 kg N/ha)	3.8	5.2	4.5	6.0	8.1	7.1	17.91	35.70	26.80
LSD at (0.05)	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.5	0.3	1.33	2.19	1.26

Rice response to N application with different irrigation schedules

L. R. Bhuiyan, N. Islam, and G. Mowla, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Gazipur 1701, Bangladesh

To determine a suitable time for N and irrigation water application to maximize yield, we conducted studies at two sites in the Ganges-Kobadak (G.K.) irrigation project area.

BR11 was used in T. aman season (Jul-Dec) plantings in 1988 and 1989, and BRL in aus (Mar-Jul) 1988. Soil was silty loam with pH 7.5-8.0, 0.80-0.85% organic matter, and CEC 18-20 meq/100 g soil. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

NPK were applied at 80-26-33 kg/ha as urea (45% N), TSP (20% P), and

KCl (50% K). All the TSP and KCl were applied basal and urea was topdressed in three equal splits at 10-d intervals from transplanting. The treatments are in the table. Approximately 5-7 cm water was applied during each irrigation.

Soil incorporation of fertilizer N (T3) produced the highest rice yield in both locations. Compared with the control (T1), rice yield increased by 11-38% for T3 and by 5-29% for T2.

The low yield in T1 may be attributed to denitrification and washing out of N with deep percolating water and surface runoff. T3 may have minimized such loss of N.

This study suggests that to maximize yields in rotational gravity irrigation systems like the G.K. project, fertilizer N should be applied at the end of irrigation and should be incorporated. ■

Incorporation of *S. rostrata* alone gave as much grain yield as did control.

Increasing applied N with *S. rostrata* further increased grain yield. However straw yields in control and with 50 kg N/ha at *S. rostrata* incorporation were similar (Table 2).

S. rostrata gave significantly higher N for plant uptake than did control. ■

Yield response of modern rice varieties to fertilizer N applied at different times of irrigation at 2 sites in the G.K. project area.

Treatment no. ^a	Mean yield ^b (t/ha)	
	Swastipur	Shaillkupa
<i>T. aman 1988</i>		
1	4.3 c	3.7 c
2	5.0 b	4.5 b
3	5.4 a	4.8 a
<i>Aus 1989</i>		
1	3.4 b	3.9 b
2	4.3 a	4.4 b
3	4.6 a	5.5 a
<i>T. aman 1989</i>		
1	4.2	4.9 b
2	4.5	5.8 a
3	4.7	6.3 a

^a 1 = fertilizer N applied 1 d before irrigation; 2 = fertilizer N applied after completion of irrigation, 3 = fertilizer N applied after completion of irrigation, followed by incorporation the following day. ^b In a column, values followed by a common letter do not vary significantly (LSD).

Integrated pest management — diseases

Effect of inoculum source on sheath blight (ShB) development

N. R. Sharma and P. S. Teng, Plant Pathology Division, IRRRI; and F. M. Olivares, Philippine Rice Research Institute, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines

IR72 (highly susceptible), IR64 (susceptible), and IR26957-86-2 (moderately resistant) were inoculated at booting stage with four ShB inoculum sources in a screenhouse experiment during 1989 dry season. The sources were 1) mycelial blocks of *Rhizoctonia solani* from a 5-d-

old culture on potato dextrose agar (PDA), 2) sclerotia from a 10-d-old culture on PDA, 3) 1-wk-old culture from rice grain-hull mixture, and 4) freshly infected rice stems from a field of IR72.

Rice grain-hull inoculum and infected stems were placed directly at the base of each hill. Mycelial discs and sclerotia were placed in tissue paper at the base of the rice plant.

Highest relative lesion height was used to determine disease development from 5 plants in each pot up to 6 times at 5-d intervals.

Disease development differed significantly (see table). In control pots where

Area under disease progress curve (AUDPC) based on highest relative lesion height (%) of 3 rice cultivars inoculated with different inoculum sources in the screenhouse, 1989.^a

Treatment	AUDPC		
	IR64	IR72	IR26957-86-2
Mycelia	922.94 ay	1121.06 ax	703.25 az
Rice grain-hull	971.19 ax	1068.63 ax	680.00 ay
Sclerotia	974.69 ax	1046.38 ax	780.50 ay
Infected rice stem	422.63 bx	378.81 bx	420.81 bx
Control	0.00cx	0.00cx	0.00cx
CV (%)			
Cultivar -	15.49		
Treatment -	19.66		

^a Mean of 4 replications. Means followed by a common letter in a column (a, b, c) or in a row (x, y, z) are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.